

Fuzzy e-paraopen Sets and Maps in Fuzzy Topological Spaces

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Abstract

The fuzzy e-paraopen and fuzzy e-paraclosed set notions in fuzzy topological spaces are the focus of this essay. In addition, we go on to examine the characteristics of a small subset of fuzzy maps, including those that are e-paracontinuous, -fuzzy e-paracontinuous, e-parairresolute, minimum e-paracontinuous, and maximum e-paracontinuous.

Keywords: Fuzzy e-paraopen, fuzzy e-paracontinuous, fuzzy minimal e-paracontinuous, fuzzy maximal e-paracontinuous.

I. Introduction

Following Chang's [2] development of fuzzy topology, Zadeh [10] constructed fuzzy sets. Ittanagi investigated fuzzy minimum (maximal) open sets in [3] while Wali investigated paraopen sets in [4]. Afterwards, the concept of mean open set was presented and shown by Mukherjee and Bagchi in [1]. In this article's part II, we explore some comparison findings and present the concept of fuzzy e-paraopen sets. In Section III, we provide many maps and examine their outcomes using suitable instances. These maps include fuzzy e-paracontinuous, -fuzzy e-paracontinuous, fuzzy e-parairresolute, fuzzy minimum e-paracontinuous, and fuzzy maximum e-paracontinuous. Fuzzy e-open, fuzzy e-paraopen, fuzzy e-paraclosed, fuzzy minimum e-open, fuzzy maximal e-open, and fuzzy maximal e-closed are variously abbreviated as Fe-O, Fe-PO, Fe-PC, FMie-O, FMie-C, FMAe-O, and FMAe-C in this study. F and Y are the acronyms for "fuzzy topological spaces" in this work.

The following terms are sometimes abbreviated as f.e-c, f.e- pc, f.mi.e-c, f.ma.e-pc, f.ma.e-pc, f.mi.e-p.i, and f.ma.e-p.i, respectively: fuzzy e-continuous, fuzzy e-paracontinuous, fuzzy minimal e-continuous, fuzzy maximal e-paracontinuous, and fuzzy maximal e-parairresolute.

Definition 1.1 A fuzzy subset ξ of a space F is called fuzzy regular open [3] (resp. fuzzy regular closed) if $\xi = \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(\xi))$ (resp. $\xi = \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(\xi))$).

The fuzzy δ -interior of a fuzzy subset ξ of F is the union of all fuzzy regular open sets contained in ξ . A fuzzy subset ξ is called fuzzy δ -open [9] if $\xi = \text{Int}\delta(\xi)$. The complement of fuzzy δ -open set is called fuzzy δ -closed (i.e., $\xi = \text{Cl}\delta(\xi)$).

Definition 1.2 A fuzzy subset ξ of a fts F is called fuzzy e-open [8] if $\xi = \text{cl}(\text{int}\delta\xi) \cap \text{int}(\text{cl}\delta\xi)$ and fuzzy e-closed set if

$$\xi = \text{cl}(\text{int}\delta\xi) \cap \text{int}(\text{cl}\delta\xi).$$

Definition 1.3 [7] A proper nonzero fuzzy e-open set α of F is said to be a (i) fuzzy minimal e-open if 1_F and α are only fuzzy e-open sets contained in α . (ii) fuzzy maximal e-open if 1_F and α are only fuzzy e-open sets containing α .

Definition 1.4 A map from fts F to another fts Y is called,

- (i) fuzzy minimal e-continuous [7] if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a fuzzy e-open set on F for any fuzzy minimal e-open set λ on Y .
- (ii) fuzzy maximal e-continuous [7] if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a fuzzy e-open set on F for any fuzzy maximal e-open set λ on Y .

II. FUZZY e-PARAOPEN AND SOME of THEIR PROPERTIES

Definition 2.1 A Fe-O set β of a fts F is said to be a Fe-PO set if is neither FMIE-O nor FMAe-O set. The complement of Fe-PO set is Fe-PC set.

Remark 2.2 It could be clear from definitions that every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set and every Fe-PC set is a Fe-C set converse is not true as shown in the succeeding example.

Example 2.3 Let $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 be fuzzy sets on $F = \{a, b, c\}$. Then $\beta_1 = 0.5/a + 0.8/b + 0.8/c$, $\beta_2 = 0.5/a + 0.8/b + 0.9/c$, $\beta_3 = 1.0/a + 0.9/b + 0.8/c$ and $\beta_4 = 1.0/a + 0.9/b + 0.9/c$ be fuzzy sets

with $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{0_F, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, 1_F\}$, Then $FM_O(F) = \{\beta_1\}$, $FMAe_O(F) = \{\beta_4\}$, $FM_C(F) = \{\beta_4^c\}$, $FMAe_C(F) = \{\beta_1^c\}$, $FP_O(F) = \{\beta_2, \beta_3\}$, $FP_C(F) = \{\beta_2^c, \beta_3^c\}$. Here β_1 is a Fe-O set but not a Fe-PO set and β_4 is a fuzzy e-closed set but not a Fe-PC set.

Remark 2.4 The succeeding example revealed that union and intersection of Fe-PO (resp. Fe-PC) sets need not be a Fe-PO (resp. Fe-PC).

Example 2.5 In example 2.3, fuzzy sets β_2, β_3 are Fe-PO sets but $\beta_2 \vee \beta_3 = \beta_4$ and $\beta_2 \wedge \beta_3 = \beta_1$ which are not Fe-PO sets. Similarly for the Fe-PC sets β_2^c, β_3^c but $\beta_2^c \vee \beta_3^c = \beta_4^c$ and $\beta_2^c \wedge \beta_3^c = \beta_1^c$ which are not Fe-PC sets.

Theorem 2.6 Let α be a nonzero proper Fe-PO subset of F . Then there exists a FMIE-O set β such that $\beta < \alpha$.

Proof. Since the definition of FMIE-O set, we can conclude that $\beta < \alpha$.

Theorem 2.7 Let α be a nonzero proper Fe-PO subset of F . Then there exists a FMAe-O set P such that $\alpha < P$.

Proof. Since the definition of FMAe-O set, we can conclude that $\alpha < P$.

Theorem 2.8 (i) Let α be a Fe-PO and β be a FMIE-O set in F . Then $\alpha \wedge \beta = 0_F$ or $\beta < \alpha$.

(ii)i) Let α be a Fe-PO and $\tau 1$ be a FMAe-O set in F . then $\alpha \vee \tau 1 = 1 F$ or $\alpha < \tau 1$.

(iii) Intersection of Fe-PO sets is either Fe-PO or FMIE-O set.

Proof. (i) Let α be a Fe-PO and β be a FMIE-O set in F . Then $\alpha \wedge \beta = 0 F$ or $\alpha \wedge \beta \neq 0 F$. Suppose $\alpha \wedge \beta = 0 F$, then we need not prove anything. Assume $\alpha \beta \not\subset 0 F$. Then we get $\alpha \beta$ is a Fe-O set and $\alpha \beta < \beta$. Hence $\beta < \alpha$.

(ii) Let α be a Fe-PO and γ be a FMAe-O set in F . Then $\alpha \vee \gamma = 1 F$ or $\alpha \vee \gamma \neq 1 F$. Assume $\alpha \vee \gamma = 1 F$, then we need not prove anything. Suppose $\alpha \vee \gamma \not\subset 1 F$. Then we get $\alpha \vee \gamma$ is a Fe-O set and $\alpha < \alpha \vee \gamma$. Since γ is a FMAe-O set, $\alpha \vee \gamma = \gamma$ which implies $\alpha < \gamma$.

(iii) Let α and η be a Fe-PO sets in F . As $\alpha \wedge \eta$ is a Fe-PO set then we need not prove anything. Assume $\alpha \wedge \eta$ is not a Fe-PO set. Since definition, $\alpha \wedge \eta$ is a FMIE-O or FMAe-O set. If $\alpha \wedge \eta$ is a f.mi. e-open set then we need not prove anything. Suppose $\alpha \wedge \eta$ is a FMAe-O set. Now $\alpha \wedge \eta < \alpha$ and $\alpha \wedge \eta < \eta$ which contradicts the fact that α and η are Fe-PO sets. Therefore $\alpha \wedge \eta$ is not a FMAe-O set. That is $\alpha \wedge \eta$ must be a FMIE-O set.

Theorem 2.9 A subset $\tau 1$ of F is Fe-PC iff it is neither FMAe-C nor FMIE-C set.

Proof. Since the definition of FMAe-C set and the fact that the complement of FMIE-O set is FMAe-C set and the complement of FMAe-O set is FMIE-C set.

Theorem 2.10 Let F be a fts and $\tau 1$ be a nonzero Fe-PC subset of F . Then there exists a f.mi.e-c set P such that $P < \tau 1$.

Proof. Since the definition of FMIE-C set we can conclude that $P < \tau 1$.

Theorem 2.11 Let F be a fts and $\tau 1$ be a nonzero Fe-PC subset of F . Then there exists a f.ma. closet set Q such that $\tau 1 < Q$. Proof. Since the definition of FMAe-C set we can conclude that $\tau 1 < Q$.

Theorem 2.12 Let F be a fts.

(i) Let δ be a Fe-PC and τ be a FMIE-C set. Then $\delta \wedge \tau = 0 F$ or $\tau < \delta$.

(ii) Let δ be a Fe-PC and γ be a FMAe-C set. Then $\delta \vee \gamma = 1 F$ or $\delta < \gamma$.

(iii) Intersection of Fe-PC sets is either Fe-PC or FMIE-C set.

Proof. (i) Let δ be a Fe-PC and τ be a FMIE-C set in F . Then $(1 F - \delta)$ is Fe-PO and $(1 F - \tau)$ is FMAe-O set in F . By Theorem 2.8(ii) we have $(1 F - \delta) \vee (1 F - \tau) = F$ or $(1 F - \delta) < (1 F - \tau)$ which implies $1 F - (\delta \wedge \tau) = 1 F$ or $\tau < \delta$. Therefore $\delta \wedge \tau = 0 F$ or

(ii) Let δ be a Fe-PC and γ be a FMAe-C set in F . Then $(1 F - \delta)$ is Fe-PO and $(1 F - \gamma)$ is FMIE-O sets in F . By Theorem 2.8(i) we have $(1 F - \delta) \wedge (1 F - \gamma) = 0 F$ or $1 F - \gamma < 1 F - \delta$ which implies $1 F - (\delta \vee \gamma) = 0 F$ or $\delta < \gamma$. Therefore $\delta \vee \gamma = 1 F$ or

(iii) Let δ and η be a Fe-PC sets in F . As $\delta \wedge \eta$ is a Fe-PC set then nothing to prove. Assume $\delta \wedge \eta$ is not a Fe-PC set. By definition, $\delta \wedge \eta$ is a FMIE-C or FMAe-C set. If $\delta \wedge \eta$ is a f.mi. e-closed set, then nothing to prove. Suppose $\delta \wedge \eta$ is a FMAe-C set. Now $\delta < \delta \wedge \eta$ and $\eta < \delta \wedge \eta$

which contradicts the fact that δ and η are Fe-PC sets. Therefore $\delta \wedge \eta$ is not a FMAe-C set. That is $\delta \wedge \eta$ must be a FMle-C set.

III. FUZZY E-PARACONTINUOUS MAPS AND SOME OF THEIR PROPERTIES

Definition 3.1 A map ψ from fts F to another fts Δ is called

- (i) f.e-pc if $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is a Fe-O set on F for every Fe-PO set α on Δ .
- (ii) *-f.e-pc if $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is a Fe-PO set on F for every Fe-O set α on Δ .
- (iii) f.e-p.i if $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is a Fe-PO set on F for every Fe-PO set α on Δ .
- (iv) f.mi.e-pc if $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is a Fe-PO set on F for every FMle-O set α on Δ .
- (v) f.ma.e-pc if $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is a Fe-PO set on F for every FMAe-O set α on Δ .

Theorem 3.2 Every f.e-c map is f.e-pc but not conversely.

Proof. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be a f.e-c map. We have to prove ψ is f.e-pc. Let α be any Fe-PO set in Δ . Since every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set, α is Fe-O set in Δ . Since ψ is a f.e-c, $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is Fe-O set in F . Hence ψ is a f.e-pc.

Example 3.3 Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_1^c, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$ and α_5 be fuzzy sets on $F = \{a, b, c\}$ with

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0.4}{c}, \alpha_2 = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0.5}{c}, \alpha_3 = \frac{0.6}{a} + \frac{0.5}{b} + \frac{0.4}{c}, \alpha_4 = \frac{0.6}{a} + \frac{0.5}{b} + \frac{0.5}{c}, \alpha_5 = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{0.6}{b} + \frac{0.4}{c} \text{ and } \alpha_1^c = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{0.6}{b} + \frac{0.5}{c}.$$

Let $\tau_1 = \{0_F, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, 1_F\}$ and $\tau_2 = \{0_F, \alpha_1, \alpha_1^c, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5, 1_F\}$ be fuzzy topologies on F . Consider the fuzzy identity mapping $\psi : (F, \tau_1) \rightarrow (F, \tau_2)$. Then ψ is f.e-pc but not f.e-c mapping because for a Fe-O set α_5 on (F, τ_2) , $\psi^{-1}(\alpha_5) = \alpha_5$ which is not a Fe-O set on (F, τ_1) .

Theorem 3.4 Every *-f.e-pc is f.e-c but not conversely.

Proof. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be a *-f.e-pc map. We have to prove ψ is f.e-c. Let α be a Fe-O set in Δ . Since ψ is *-f.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is Fe-PO set in F . Since every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set, $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is Fe-O set in F . Hence ψ is a f.e-c.

Example 3.5 Let β_1, β_2 and β_3 be fuzzy sets on $F = \Delta = \{a, b, c\}$. Then $\beta_1 = 1.0/a + 0.0/b + 0.0/c$, $\beta_2 = 1.0/a + 0.6/b + 0.0/c$ and $\beta_3 = 1.0/a + 0.6/b + 0.5/c$ are defined as follows: Consider $\mathfrak{T}_1 = \{0_F, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, 1_F\}$, let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be an identity mapping. Then ψ is f.e-c but not *-f.e-pc mapping since for the Fe-O set β_3 on Δ , $\psi^{-1}(\beta_3) = \beta_3$ which is not a Fe-PO set on F .

Theorem 3.6 Every *-f.e-pc is f.e-pc but not conversely.

Proof. The proof follows from Theorems 3.2 and 3.4.

Example 3.7 In Example 3.5, “ ψ is f.e-pc map but it is not *-f.e-pc map.”

Theorem 3.8 Every f.e-p.i map is f.e-pc but not conversely.

Proof. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be a f.e-p.i map. We have to prove that ψ is f.e-pc. Let α be any Fe-PO set in Δ . Since ψ is f.e-p.i, $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is Fe-PO set in F . Since every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set, $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is Fe-O set in F . Hence ψ is a f.e-pc map.

Example 3.9 As described in Example 3.5, consider $\mathfrak{F}_3 = \{0_F, \beta_2, \beta_3, 1_F\}$ and $\mathfrak{F}_1 = \{0_\Delta, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, 1_\Delta\}$. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be an identity mapping. Then ψ is f.e-pc but not f.e-p.i mapping since for the Fe-PO set β_2 on Δ , $\psi^{-1}(\beta_2) = \beta_2$ which is not a Fe-PO set on F .

Theorem 3.10 Every *-f.e-pc is f.e-p.i but not conversely.

Proof. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be a f.e-pc map. We have to prove that ψ is f.e-p.i. Let α be a Fe-PO set in Δ . Since every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set, α is a Fe-O set. Since ψ is *-f.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is Fe-PO set in F . Hence ψ is a f.e-p.i map.

Example 3.11 In Example 3.5, “ ψ is f.e-p.i map but it is not -f.e-pc map.”

Remark 3.12 Fuzzy e-p.irresolute and f.e-c maps are independent of each other.

Example 3.13 In Example 3.3, ψ is f.e-p.i map but it is not f.e-c map because for the Fe-O set β_5 on Δ , $\psi^{-1}(\beta_5) = \beta_5$ which is not a Fe-O set on F .

Let $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ be fuzzy sets on $\blacksquare = \{a, b, c\}$ and let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ be fuzzy sets on $\Delta = \{x, y, z\}$. Then $\beta_1 = 0.2/a + 0.2/b + 0.2/c$, $\beta_2 = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0.3}{b} + \frac{0.3}{c}$, $\beta_3 = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{0.7}{c}$, $\alpha_1 = \frac{0.2}{x} + \frac{0.0}{y} + \frac{0.2}{z}$, $\alpha_2 = \frac{0.7}{x} + \frac{0.0}{y} + \frac{0.7}{z}$, $\alpha_3 = \frac{0.7}{x} + \frac{0.7}{y} + \frac{0.7}{z}$ are defined as follows:

Consider $\mathfrak{F}_1 = \{0_F, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, 1_F\}$, $\mathfrak{F}_2 = \{0_\Delta, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, 1_\Delta\}$. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be a fuzzy mapping defined as $f(a) = f(b) = f(c) = y$. Then ψ is f.e-c but not fuzzy e-p.irresolute because for the Fe-PO set α_2 on Δ , $\psi^{-1}(\alpha_2) = 0_F$ which is not a Fe-PO set on F .

Theorem 3.14 Every f.mi.e-pc map is f.mi. e-continuous but not conversely.

Proof. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be a f.mi.e-pc map. We have to prove that ψ is f.mi. e-continuous. Let τ_1 be any FMiE-O set in Δ . Since ψ is f.mi.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is Fe-PO set in F . Since every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set, $\psi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-O set in F . Hence ψ is a fuzzy minimal e-continuous.

Example 3.15 From Example 3.2, ψ is f.mi. e-continuous but it is not a f.mi. e-p.continuous, since for the FMiE-O β_1 on Δ , $\psi^{-1}(\beta_1) = \beta_1$ which is not a Fe-PO set on F .

Remark 3.16 Fuzzy minimal e-p.continuous and f.e-pc (resp. f.e-c) are independent of each other.

Example 3.17 Let β_1, β_2 be fuzzy sets on $F = \{a, b, c\}$ and let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ be fuzzy sets on $\Delta = \{x, y, z\}$. Then $\beta_1 = 0.5/a + 0.0/b + 0.0/c$, $\beta_2 = 0.5/a + 0.7/b + 0.0/c$, $\beta_3 = 0.5/a + 0.7/b + 0.1/c$, $\beta_2 = \frac{0.5}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{0.0}{c}$, $\beta_3 = \frac{0.5}{a} + \frac{0.7}{b} + \frac{0.1}{c}$, $\alpha_1 = \frac{0.5}{x} + \frac{0.7}{y} + \frac{0.0}{z}$, $\alpha_2 = \frac{0.5}{x} + \frac{0.7}{y} + \frac{0.9}{z}$, $\alpha_3 = \frac{0.5}{x} + \frac{0.8}{y} + \frac{0.0}{z}$ and $\alpha_4 = \frac{0.5}{x} + \frac{0.8}{y} + \frac{0.9}{z}$ are defined as follows: Consider $\mathfrak{F}_1 = \{0_F, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, 1_F\}$, $\mathfrak{F}_2 = \{0_\Delta, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, 1_\Delta\}$. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be an identity mapping. Then ψ is f.mi.e-pc but not f.e-pc (resp. f.e-c) map because for the Fe-PO set α_3 on Δ , $\psi^{-1}(\alpha_3) = \alpha_3$ which is not a Fe-O set on F . In Example 3.2, ψ is f.e-pc but not f.mi.e-pc.

Theorem 3.18 Every f.ma.e-pc is f.ma.e-c but not conversely.

Proof. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be a f.ma.e-pc map. To prove ψ is f.mi. e-continuous. Let δ be any FMAe-O set in Δ . Since ψ is f.ma.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\delta)$ is Fe-PO set in F . Since every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set, $\psi^{-1}(\delta)$ is a Fe-O set in F . Hence ψ is a f.ma.e-c.

Example 3.19 In Example 3.2, “ ψ is f.ma.e-c but it is not f.ma.e-pc map.”

Remark 3.20 Fuzzy maximal e-p.continuous and f.e-pc (resp. f.e-c) are independent of each other.

Example 3.21 Let β_1, β_2 be fuzzy sets on $F = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ be fuzzy sets on $\Delta = \{x, y, z, w\}$. Then $\beta_1 = 0.0/a + 0.0/b + 0.0/c + 0.9/d$, $\beta_2 = 0.0/a + 0.0/b + 0.7/c + 0.9/d$, $\beta_3 = 0.0/a + 0.5/b + 0.7/c + 0.9/d$, $\beta_4 = 0.2/a + 0.5/b + 0.7/c + 0.9/d$, $\alpha_1 = 0.0/a + 0.0/b + 0.3/c + 0.0/d$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0/a + 0.0/b + 0.3/c + 0.9/d$, $\alpha_3 = 0.0/a + 0.5/b + 0.7/c + 0.9/d$, are defined as follows: Consider $F_1 = \{0_F, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, 1_F\}$, $F_2 = \{0_\Delta, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, 1_\Delta\}$.

Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be an identity mapping. Then ψ is f.ma.e-pc but not f.e-pc (resp. f.e-c) map because for the Fe-PO set α_2 on Δ , $\psi^{-1}(\alpha_2) = \alpha_2$ which is not a Fe-O set on F . In Example 3.2, ψ is f.e-pc (resp. f.e-c) but not f.ma.e-pc.

Remark 3.22 Fuzzy minimal e-p.continuous and f.ma.e-pc are independent of each other.

Example 3.23 In Example 3.17, “ ψ is f.mi.e-pc map but it is not f.ma.e-pc map. From Example III, ψ is f.ma.e-pc map but it is not f.mi.e-pc map.”

Theorem 3.24 Let F and Δ be fts. A map $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is a f.e-pc iff the inverse image of each Fe-PC set in Δ is a fuzzy e-closed set in F .

Proof. Obvious.

Theorem 3.25 Let A be a nonzero fuzzy subset of F . If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-pc then the restriction map $\psi_A : A \rightarrow \Delta$ is a f.e-pc.

Proof. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be a f.e-pc map and $A \subset F$. To prove ψ_A is a f.e-pc. Let α be a Fe-PO set in Δ . Since ψ is f.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is a Fe-O set in F . By the definition of relative topology $f_A^{-1}(\alpha) = A \wedge \psi^{-1}(\alpha)$. Therefore $A \wedge \psi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is a Fe-O set in A . Hence ψ_A is a f.e-pc.

Remark 3.26 The composition of f.e-pc maps need not be f.e-pc.

Example 3.27 Let $F = \Delta = \Phi = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and the fuzzy sets $\beta_1 = 0.0/a + 0.0/b + 0.2/c + 0.0/d$, $\beta_2 = 0.0/a + 0.0/b + 0.2/c + 0.5/d$, $\beta_3 = 0.0/a + 0.7/b + 0.2/c + 0.5/d$ and $\beta_4 = 0.3/a + 0.7/b + 0.2/c + 0.5/d$ are defined as follows: consider $\mathfrak{F}_1 = \{0_F, \beta_1, \beta_2, 1_F\}$, $\mathfrak{F}_2 = \{0_\Delta, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, 1_\Delta\}$ and $F_3 = \{0_\Phi, \beta_1, \beta_3, \beta_4, 1_\Phi\}$. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ be identity mappings. Then ψ and ξ are f.e-pc maps $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is not f.e-pc, since for the Fe-PO set β_3 in Φ , $\psi^{-1}(\beta_3) = \beta_3$ which is not Fe-O set in F .

Theorem 3.28 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-c and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is f.e-pc. Then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.e-pc.

Proof. Let τ_1 be any Fe-PO set in Φ . As ξ is f.e-pc, $\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-O set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-c, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-O set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is a f.e-pc. $\square$

Theorem 3.29 Let F and Δ be fts. A map $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is -f.e-pc iff the inverse image of each fuzzy e-closed set in Δ is a Fe-PC set in F .

Proof. Obvious.

Remark 3.30 Let F and Δ be fts. If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is *-f.e-pc, then the restriction map $\psi_A : A \rightarrow \Delta$ need not be *-f.e-pc.

Example 3.31 Let $F = \Delta = \Phi = \{a, b, c\}$ and the fuzzy sets $\beta_1 = 0.7/a + 0.0/b + 0.0/c$, $\beta_2 = 0.7/a + 0.3/b + 0.0/c$ and $\beta_3 = 0.7/a + 0.3/b + 0.5/c$ are defined as follows: Consider $F = \{0, \beta, \beta, \beta, 1, F\}$ and $\delta_1 = \{0_\Delta, \beta_2, 1_\Delta\}$. Let $\delta = \frac{0.0}{a} + \frac{0.3}{b} + \frac{0.9}{c}$ be a fuzzy set with $F\delta = \{0\delta, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \delta\}$ where $\beta_4 = 0.0/a + 0.3/b + 0.0/c$ and $\beta_5 = 0.0/a + 0.3/b + 0.5/c$. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be an identity map. Then ψ is *-f.e-pc but $f\delta : F\delta \rightarrow \Delta$ is not a *-f.e-pc, since for the Fe-O set β_2 in Δ , $\psi^{-1}(\beta_2) = \beta_2$ which is not a Fe-PO set in $F\delta$.

Theorem 3.32 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is *-f.e-pc, then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a *-f.e-pc.

Proof. Let τ_1 be any Fe-PO set in Φ . As every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set, $\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is fuzzy

*-f.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is a *-f.e-pc. $\square$

Theorem 3.33 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-pc and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is *-f.e-pc, then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.e-pc (resp. f.e-c).

Proof. Let τ_1 be any Fe-PO (resp. Fe-O) set in Φ . As every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set, $\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Since ξ is a *-f.e-pc, $\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-O set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.e-pc (resp. f.e-c) map.

Theorem 3.34 A map $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-p.i iff the inverse image of each fuzzy are e-paraclosed set in Δ is a Fe-PC set in F .

Proof. Straightforward.

Remark 3.35 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-p.i. Then the restriction map $\psi_A : A \rightarrow \Delta$ need not be f.e-p.i.

Example 3.36 In Example 3.2, let $\delta = 0.0/a + 0.0/b + 0.6/c$ be a fuzzy set with $F\delta = \{0\delta, \beta_4, \delta\}$ where $\beta_4 = 0.0/a + 0.0/b + 0.5/c$. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ be an identity map. Then ψ is f.e-p.i but $f\delta : F\delta \rightarrow \Delta$ is not a f.e-p.i, since for the Fe-PO set β_2 in Δ , $\psi^{-1}(\beta_2) = \beta_2$ which is not a Fe-PO set in $F\delta$.

Theorem 3.37 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-pc and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is f.e-p.i, then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.e-pc.

Proof. Let τ_1 be a Fe-PO set in Φ . As ξ is a f.e-p.i, $\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-O set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.e-pc. $\square$

Theorem 3.38 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ are f.e-p.i, then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.e-p.i.

Proof. Let τ_1 be a Fe-PO set in Φ . Since ξ is a f.e-p.i, $\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-p.i, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)) =$

$(\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.e-pc.

Theorem 3.39 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is *-f.e-pc and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is f.e-p.i. Then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.e-p.i.

Proof. Let τ_1 be a Fe-PO set in Φ . As ξ is a f.e-p.i, $\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Since every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set, we have

$\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-O set in Δ . Again since ψ is *-f.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.e-p.i. $\square$

Theorem 3.40 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-p.i and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is *-f.e-pc, then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.e-p.i.

Proof. Let τ_1 be a Fe-PO set in Φ . As every Fe-PO set is a Fe-O set, τ_1 is a Fe-O set in Φ . Since ξ is a f.e-pc, $\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-p.i, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\tau_1)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\tau_1)$ is a Fe-PO set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.e-p.i mapping. $\square$

Theorem 3.41 A map $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.mi. f.e-pc iff the inverse image of each FMAe-C set in Δ is a Fe-PC set in F .

Proof. Obvious.

Remark 3.42 The composition of f.mi.e-pc maps need not be a f.mi.e-pc.

Example 3.43 Let $F = \Delta = \Phi = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and the fuzzy sets $\tau_1 = 0.0/a + 0.0/b + 0.2/c + 0.4/d$, $\tau_2 = 0.0/a + 0.7/b + 0.2/c + 0.4/d$, $\tau_3 = 0.2/a + 0.7/b + 0.2/c + 0.4/d$ and $\tau_4 = 0.3/a + 0.7/b + 0.2/c + 0.4/d$ are defined as follows: consider $\mathfrak{F}_1 = \{0_F, \tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3, 1_F\}$, $\mathfrak{F}_2 = \{0_\Delta, \tau_2, \tau_3, \tau_4, 1_\Delta\}$ and $\mathfrak{F}_3 = \{0_\Phi, \tau_3, \tau_4, 1_\Phi\}$. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ be identity mappings. Then ψ and ξ are f.mi.e-pc maps $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is not f.mi.e-pc, since for the FMie-O set τ_3 in Φ , $\psi^{-1}(\tau_3) = \tau_3$ which is not Fe-PO set in F .

Theorem 3.44 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-p.i and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is f.mi.e-pc, then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.mi.e-pc. Proof. Let η be a FMie-O set in Φ . As ξ is f.mi.e-pc, $\xi^{-1}(\eta)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-p.i, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\eta)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\eta)$ is a Fe-PO set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.mi.e-pc map.

$\square$

Theorem 3.45 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-pc and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is f.mi.e-pc, then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.mi.e-pc. Proof. Let η be a FMie-O set in Φ . Since ξ is f.mi.e-pc, $\xi^{-1}(\eta)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\eta)) =$

$(\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\eta)$ is a Fe-O set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.mi.e-pc mapping.

Theorem 3.46 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-p.i and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is *-f.e-pc, then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.mi.e-pc.

Proof. Let η be a FMie-O set in Φ . As every f.mi. e-open set is a Fe-O set, η is an e-open set in Φ . Since ψ is *-f.e-pc, $\xi^{-1}(\eta)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-p.i $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\eta)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\eta)$ is a Fe-PO set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.mi.e-pc.

Theorem 3.47 Let F and Δ be fts. A map $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.ma.e-pc iff the inverse image of each FMie-C set in Δ is a Fe-PC set in F .

Proof. Sraightforward.

Remark 3.48 The composition of f.ma.e-pc maps need not be a f.ma.e-pc.

Example 3.49 Let $F = \Delta = \Phi = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and the fuzzy sets $\tau_1 = 0.0/a + 0.1/b + 0.0/c + 0.0/d$, $\tau_2 = 0.0/a + 0.1/b + 0.7/c + 0.0/d$, $\tau_3 = 0.0/a + 0.1/b + 0.7/c + 0.2/d$ and $\tau_4 = 0.3/a + 0.1/b + 0.7/c + 0.2/d$ are defined as follows: consider $\mathfrak{F}_1 = \{0_F, \tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3, 1_F\}$, $\mathfrak{F}_2 = \{0_\Delta, \tau_2, \tau_3, \tau_4, 1_\Delta\}$ and $\mathfrak{F}_3 = \{0_\Phi, \tau_3, \tau_4, 1_\Phi\}$. Let $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ and $g : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ be identity mappings. Then ψ and ξ are f.ma.e-pc maps $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is not f.ma.e-pc, since for the FMAe-O set τ_2 in Φ , $\psi^{-1}(\tau_2) = \tau_2$ which is not Fe-PO set in F .

Theorem 3.50 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-p.i and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is f.ma.e-pc, hen $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.ma.e-pc. Proof. Let γ be a FMAe-O set in Φ . Since ξ is f.ma.e-pc, $\xi^{-1}(\gamma)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-p.i, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\gamma)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\gamma)$ is a Fe-PO set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.ma.e-pc.

Theorem 3.51 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-pc and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is f.ma.e-pc, then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.ma.e-c.

Proof. Let γ be a FMAe-O set in Φ . Since ξ is f.ma.e-pc, $\xi^{-1}(\gamma)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-pc, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\gamma)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\gamma)$ is a Fe-O set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.ma.e-c.

Theorem 3.52 If $\psi : F \rightarrow \Delta$ is f.e-p.i and $\xi : \Delta \rightarrow \Phi$ is *-f.e-pc, then $\xi \circ \psi : F \rightarrow \Phi$ is a f.ma.e-pc.

Proof. Let γ be a FMAe-O set in Φ . Since every FMAe-O set is a Fe-O set, γ is a Fe-O set in Φ . Since ξ is *-f.e-pc, $\xi^{-1}(\gamma)$ is a Fe-PO set in Δ . Again since ψ is f.e-p.i, $\psi^{-1}(\xi^{-1}(\gamma)) = (\xi \circ \psi)^{-1}(\gamma)$ is a Fe-PO set in F . Hence $\xi \circ \psi$ is f.ma.e-pc.

IV. CONCLUSION

One noteworthy idea is fuzzy e-open sets. This allowed for the introduction and study of fuzzy e-paraopen sets. Furthermore, we compared with suitable instances and used a variety of fuzzy mappings.

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